

RENEWABLE ELECTRICITY SOURCES AND THEIR EFFECTIVE USE

Ilyasov Botir Kodirovich

**Teacher of the military training center of the
National University of Uzbekistan.**

Reviewer: Sh.Djabborov

**Associate professor, head of the cycle of aviation specialties and military
transport of the military training center
of the National University of Uzbekistan**

Abstract: In this article, a general classification of renewable energy sources is given and methods of their effective use are considered. Also, information is given about the renewable sources of electricity used in our country today.

Keywords: *energy resources, fuel sources, mechanical energy, traditional energy sources, solar power plants, construction of thermal power plants, geothermal heat supply.*

The economic development of Uzbekistan is determined by the transition to market relations, the use of complex technologies that save energy resources in agro-industry sectors, and the creation of their scientific basis. Fuel heat and electricity are used in industry, agriculture, transport, and all production processes. Mechanical and electrical energy is mainly obtained by burning various fuels, water energy, and atomic nuclear energy. Economical use of fuel sources leads to the use of alternative energy sources, which are continuously renewable sources of energy. Currently, the energy obtained is mainly obtained from non-renewable energy sources. Today, the amount of natural fuel used in the world is

equivalent to 12 billion tons of oil. This means that each person needs about 2 tons of fuel. According to the data, during the last 40 years, more fuel has been exploited for consumption than the organic fuel mined during the entire history of mankind. This causes their reserves to decrease rapidly. If the population reaches 9-10 billion people by 2050, the need for energy will increase 3 times. From the above, it can be said that rational use of existing energy sources requires increasing the share of alternative energy sources in the energy system.

Currently, many technologies are proposed in the field of renewable and non-traditional energy sources that can be easily implemented. However, in addition to the undeniable advantages of renewable and non-conventional energy sources (HW and NEM), the cost of the power obtained because it is scattered on the earth also increases [1]. Therefore, for now, the use of QT and NEM conventional energy sources cannot compete with the use of conventional energy sources. Nevertheless, the progress achieved through the implementation of some scientific and technical solutions already shows that they will pay off economically in the coming years. According to the data, by 2020, 2.6 billion tons of conditional fuel can be saved as a result of the use of renewable and non-traditional energy sources (QT and NEM). The main directions and program for the development of renewable energy research are as follows.

- a) production and operation of steam pipe solar power plants;
- b) design and production of autonomous (photoelectric for consumers) devices;
- d) design and construction of solar hot water supply, heating, and air condensation systems;
- e) construction and operation of geo IES;
- f) design and construction of geothermal heat supply;
- g) design and implementation of wind power units and wind power plants (WPPs);

According to the analysis of energy resources currently used by the population on Earth, coal accounts for 51.1%, gas for 13.5%, oil products for 12.5%, uranium energy used in nuclear power plants for 10.7%, alternative energy sources (MEM) is 13.2 percent. In general, energy sources used in nature can be divided into two groups. Alternative energy sources are divided into renewable and non-renewable energy sources. Renewable energy sources include the use of solar, wind, running water sources, rising and falling energy from ocean and seawater, geothermal energy, biogas, and gas extraction from household waste. Today, in our country, some experiments have been conducted on the use of renewable alternative energy sources, and practical results have been achieved.

Renewable energy is energy collected from renewable sources that replenish naturally over time. It includes sources such as sunlight, wind, water movement, and geothermal heat[2]. While most renewable energy sources are sustainable, some are not. For example, some biomass energy sources are considered unsustainable in their current operation. Renewable energy often generates energy to generate electricity for the electric grid, air and water heating and cooling, and self-contained energy systems. From 2011 to 2021, renewable energy has grown from 20% to 28% of the global electricity supply system. Fossil energy decreased from 68% to 62%, and nuclear energy from 12% to 10%. The share of hydropower decreased from 16% to 15%, while solar and wind energy increased from 2% to 10%. Biomass and geothermal energy grew between 2% and 3%. 135 countries have installed 3,146 gigawatts, while 156 countries have developed laws regulating the renewable energy sector.

The state policy in the field of renewable energy in Uzbekistan takes into account the development experience of several industrially developed and at the same time developing countries in the use of renewable energy and their scale. This showed that the establishment of clear goals and tasks in the field of renewable energy, as well as state support, will help renewable energy to be

competitive with traditional energy production technology. Although the use of renewable energy devices requires considerable investment, they are economically viable. Sulfur, nitrogen, and carbon oxides released into the air due to conventional fuel-based energy are spread over long distances. In addition, they mix with rainwater, turn into acid compounds, and fall to the ground in rain, hurting plants and soil. As a result of the increase of such acids in the environment, heavy metals affect food and ultimately the human body through these products. In this case, one harm brings another harm along with it.

Renewable energy is continuously renewable in the earth's biosphere and inexhaustible on a human scale. They are solar energy, wind, ocean, river, underground mines, and bioenergy. The main advantage of renewable energy is its inexhaustibility and ecological purity [3]. Its use does not change the energy balance of the planet, that is, it does not affect natural processes. These qualities serve the development of renewable energy abroad, and now in our Republic. It is no secret that Uzbekistan has certain opportunities in renewable energy. The total potential is about 51 billion, but the current level of technology allows to use of 179 million T.N.E. It is more than 3 times the current annual volume of oil production.

Uzbekistan has great potential in the use of solar energy. The climatic conditions of our country are very favorable for the use of solar energy. According to the calculations of the experts of the "Physics-Solar" Scientific Research Institute of the UzR FA, the amount of solar energy falling on the territory of Uzbekistan is, on average, four times more than the energy obtained from other sources in the country. At the same time, Uzbekistan also has reserves of raw materials for obtaining crystalline silicon. On this basis, 90 percent of photovoltaic modules are produced in the whole world. Silicon deposits exist in the Jizzakh and Samarkand regions. Work is being carried out on the commissioning of factories producing technical silicon in the Navoi and Angren-

free industrial zones. This resource reserve makes it possible to organize a significant concentration of local production in the field of solar energy. Of course, many non-traditional means can replace fuel or electricity. But it is important to choose among them the one that does not harm the environment, is effective in use, and at the same time is financially acceptable. From this point of view, wind energy has several advantages. Today, this alternative energy production is very popular in Western Europe. The reason is that as the natural conditions are suitable for this, the demand for this type of energy is also increasing.

Modern SHPPs work optimally in places with a wind speed from 3-4 m/s to 25 m/s, not high about the terrain. Germany, which has such territorial capabilities, is currently the world leader in the use of wind energy. This alternative energy has several advantages from an economic and environmental point of view. For example, the construction of SPP is cheap and convenient compared to other energy sources. The main part of the cost of the produced energy is the initial expenses spent on the construction of the SPP. In addition, since the base of the station tower is usually completely underground, the possibility of planting crops is preserved in the lands near it. To put it simply, the areas reserved for such devices do not hurt agriculture. They also do not require any fuel. Most importantly, wind is inexhaustible by nature. After all, it has been determined that the power of this natural phenomenon is 100 times greater than the water energy sources available in all the rivers on Earth. All this strengthens confidence in the prospects of wind energy. There is another side to the problem, there are some problems related to the implementation of wind energy. In particular, the unstable nature of the wind affects the steady production of energy at SPPs [4]. Taking this into account, it is possible to use solar batteries in such power plants. It is in this way that traditional electricity is collected and continuous supply is achieved.

Biomass is the energy obtained by burning waste. In practice, biomass is waste. Such as dead trees or their saplings, rhizomes of plants from the garden, bark, and shavings. Such waste includes straws used as feed and bedding in livestock farms. There may be more crops: grain, cotton, corn, etc. In Odar, household waste from our house is taken to the landfill and buried. Household waste is also a type of biomass, and it can be used in the production of biofuel. It is very simple to use in biomass. Special furnaces are lit and fired in boilers, water is heated in boilers, turned into steam and turned pipes to get electricity. Biomass energy is a promising direction of energy production, production, and use of biomass. Biomass sources include solid domestic and industrial wastes, municipal sewage and sewage, animal husbandry, plant residues, forest products, in particular, wood, paper pulp, and other wastes from production in processing and shipping. enters. According to experts' calculations, biomass energy can meet 15-19 percent of Uzbekistan's energy needs. This method of energy production provides high-quality fertilizer to the country's agriculture while solving the environmental protection problem to a certain extent. Biogas can be used directly from biomass in landfills. During the digestion of waste, methane gas is released. They are collected in pipes and sent to a thermal power plant, where the mixture is mixed with natural gas and used in the production of electricity.

People have been using biogas for 200 years. Before the advent of electricity, in London, biogas was used to light the streets in special gas lamps taken from underground sewer pipes, called street "gas horn". Biogas is usually a mixture of carbon dioxide (SO₂) and methane (SN₄). It is formed by the decomposition of various biological microorganisms in a state where air and oxygen cannot enter (absence of oxygen, called "anaerobic state"). Biogas is also produced in marshes and lake bottoms due to decaying organic matter, high humidity, and lack of oxygen[5]. In addition, to the ability to live in anaerobic conditions, and the ability to produce methane, microorganisms have other

properties. They can digest cellulose, the main ingredient of wood. Another feature of these bacteria is that they are very sensitive to living conditions such as temperature, acidity, water volume, etc. Biogas equipment was successfully tested in individual poultry factories and fattening and livestock complexes. But so far it has not been widely distributed, it has not become popular. Water energy (hydropower) - when it rains in the mountains or melts ice and snow, water flows downwards from springs, streams, and water basins, forms a river from top to bottom, joins the sea and ocean, or disappears into deserts. People used the energy of running water and water falling from the hill as mechanical or electrical energy for themselves.

If the peculiarities of the climate and weather conditions are taken into account, there are enough opportunities for renewable energy sources in our country. One of the most important issues is energy, for the development of the entire economy of the region, the implementation of existing fuel and energy opportunities in effective and effective ways, as well as attracting new types of ecologically clean energy to the energy balance. Renewable energy sources (electricity, natural gas, hot water) for remote desert mountainous, waterless, seasonal jobs or expeditions that require electricity, heat, and drinking water are of decisive importance. In Uzbekistan, more than 60 percent of the population lives in rural areas. About 1,500 hard-to-reach rural settlements cannot use traditional sources of electricity. That is why the attention to programs for the use of renewable energy sources has increased sharply in the country.

Geothermal Energy – Earth's surface radiates heat energy like the sun. This energy is called geothermal energy, and it can provide people with heat and electricity. Its production does not pollute the environment, that is, it is environmentally friendly. Geothermal energy appeared 4 billion years ago as a result of the mixing of combustible gases and cosmic dust. At a depth of 6.5 thousand kilometers of the Earth's core, the temperature can rise to 5000 degrees.

In ancient times, people used boiling and hot springs that erupted from underground. Over time, he began to use these healing waters for other purposes. The ancient Romans created a heating system for their buildings using geothermal water in Pompeii. American Indians used hot springs for cooking almost 10,000 years ago[6]. Hot water, hot air, or steam energy from underground can be used to generate electricity and heat the room with current technologies.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Uzbekistan is the most favorable region in terms of the scope and duration of the use of alternative energy sources. The potential of solar energy alone in our Serkuyosh region is 95 billion. equal to a ton of conventional fuel. If the technical potential of solar energy is fully developed in our country, the annual need for all types of energy will be covered 4 times more. This, in turn, means that, along with enriching the country's energy reserves, it will also open wide opportunities for the export of mined energy resources. At the moment, scientific research is being carried out based on programs for the use of alternative energy sources in about 80 countries of the world. Solar devices are used to heat and cool buildings, obtain fresh water, generate electricity, and implement various technological processes. In the southern regions of our country, sunny days are 280-300 days a year. The average temperature in summer is 44-45 C. It is urgent to use this kind of solar energy in the national economy.

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